

Fluoro Complexes of Hexavalent Uranium. Part-XI. Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI) containing Fluoride and Malonate

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The salts of the new types $M_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]$, $M_4[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]_2$ and $M_2[(UO_2)_2F_4(C_2H_2O_4)_2]$, where $M = K$ and NH_4 , have been prepared by crystallising solutions containing UO_2F_2 and the alkali malonates in different mole ratios. The thermogravimetric analysis of the ammonium salts have been carried out. Molecular conductances of the salt solutions indicate that the complex ions are decomposed in dilute solution to a great extent. The mode of bonding of malonate group in the complexes has been examined by IR spectra.

MALONATO complexes of uranyl ion have received only scanty attention. The trihydrate, $UO_2(C_2H_2O_4) \cdot 3H_2O$ has been prepared¹ by heating $UO_2 \cdot nH_2O$ with excess of malonic acid solution. Its thermal decomposition has been studied¹. Complexes of the type $[UO_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]^{2-}$ have been reported^{2,3} with alkali and alkaline earth metals. The structures of $(NH_4)_2[UO_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2] \cdot H_2O$ and $Ba[UO_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$ have been studied^{4,5} by X-ray. An adduct of uranyl malonate with urea has been prepared⁶. A number of peroxomalonato complexes have been reported⁷. In continuation to our studies on the mixed complexes of UO_2^{2+} containing fluoride and carboxylate ions⁸⁻¹⁰, we report in this communication the isolation and characterisation of fluoromalonato complexes of UO_2^{2+} of the new ions $[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]^{2-}$, $[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]^{4-}$ and $[(UO_2)_2F_4(C_2H_2O_4)_2]^{2-}$.

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate, hydrogen peroxide, hydrofluoric acid (40%) and malonic acid used were of AnalaR or G. R. (E. Merck) quality. Preparation of the acid $H[UO_2F_2] \cdot H_2O$, starting from $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, has been described in our earlier publications^{8,11}. Uranyl fluoride was prepared by heating $H[UO_2F_2] \cdot H_2O$ in a platinum crucible at 150° to a constant weight. Potassium malonate was prepared by neutralising malonic acid with potassium hydroxide followed by complete evaporation and drying in a desiccator over caustic soda. A solution of ammonium malonate was prepared by neutralising malonic acid with ammonium hydroxide and reducing the volume on a water-bath avoiding complete evaporation.

Analysis: Methods of analysis of uranium potassium and fluorine are described in our previ-

ous papers^{8,12}. Uranium content of the ammonium salts was also determined by igniting the compounds and weighing as U_3O_8 . Nitrogen was analysed by Dumas' method. Total fluoride and malonate content was determined by passing the salt solution through a column of cation-exchange resin (Dowex 50-X8, A. R. grade, J. T. Baker Chemical Co., Phillipsberg) in hydrogen form and titrating the effluent with standard alkali solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. Uranyl ion remained fixed on the resin.

Physical measurements: Thermogravimetric analysis was done using a manual thermobalance. The sample (~100 mg) was heated at a rate of 2° per min. The conductivity measurements were made with a Systronics 303 direct reading conductivity meter using a polythene body conductivity cell. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrophotometer in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Preparation of complexes: $(NH_4)_2[(UO_2)_2F_4(C_2H_2O_4)_2]$, $(NH_4)_2[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]$ and $(NH_4)_4[UO_2F_2(C_2H_2O_4)_2]_2$. A concentrated solution of UO_2F_2 (1.0 g) was mixed with concentrated solutions of ammonium malonate in the mole ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 3 and 1 : 10, respectively, and kept in the desiccator over sulphuric acid. The yellow crystals separated after 1 day were filtered. The yields were 0.6, 0.6 and 0.8 g, respectively.

The potassium salts were prepared by following the same methods as those used for the corresponding ammonium salts replacing ammonium malonate by appropriate amounts of potassium malonate. The yields were 0.5, 0.6 and 0.8 g, respectively.

All the compounds were dried by pressing between folds of filter paper and then keeping in a

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Alkali metal or N	Equivalent of total anion ^a per U atom Found/(Calcd.)	Molecular conductance ^b $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$
	U	F			
$\text{K}_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	59.7 (59.8)	9.7 (9.5)	10.0 (9.8)	3.00 (3.0)	460
$\text{K}_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	48.6 (48.8)	7.9 (7.8)	16.2 (16.0)	3.98 (4.0)	450
$\text{K}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$	35.5 (35.6)	5.8 (5.7)	23.6 (23.4)	5.95 (6.0)	600
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	63.2 (63.1)	10.1 (10.0)	3.8 (3.7)	2.95 (3.0)	420
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	53.5 (53.4)	8.6 (8.5)	6.3 (6.2)	3.99 (4.0)	450
$(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$	40.8 (40.7)	6.6 (6.5)	10.3 (10.2)	6.00 (6.0)	590

^aTotal fluoride and malonate.

^bIn $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ aqueous solution at 25°.

desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The compounds are yellow crystalline substances, stable in air and soluble in water, but insoluble in common organic solvents. The salts $\text{M}_2[\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ and $\text{M}_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ (where $\text{M}=\text{K}$ and NH_4) can be recrystallised unchanged from water. However, recrystallisation of $\text{M}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ (where $\text{M}=\text{K}$ and NH_4) from water gave yellow products, the analyses of which did not correspond to any simple stoichiometry. The molecular conductances of the salts (Table 1) indicate that the complex ions are highly dissociated in dilute solutions.

On passing dilute solutions of the salts through a column of cation-exchange resin in hydrogen form the complex ions are completely broken up. Elution with water brought out all fluoride and malonate in the effluent. Uranyl ion was adsorbed on the bed which could be finally eluted out with dilute hydrochloric acid.

The thermograms of the three ammonium salts were recorded up to 600°. The compounds $(\text{NH}_4)_4[\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ begin to decompose at about 130°. The TGA curves of both the compounds gave horizontals stretching approximately between 340 and 460° corresponding to the formation of UO_2F_2 with the losses of 47.7 and 31.2% which correspond to the losses of two molecules and one molecule of ammonium malonate, respectively (calculated losses 47.3 and 30.9%, respectively). The compound $(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ begins to decompose at about 180°. The TGA curve of this compound gave a horizontal stretching between 360 and 450° corresponding to the formation of UO_2F_2 with a loss of 18.6% which corresponds to the loss of one molecule of ammonium malonate (calculated loss

18.3%). U_3O_8 was finally obtained by heating all the complexes upto about 520°.

The X-ray structure analysis of a very few complexes containing coordinated malonate has been made⁴. From the available data it appears that the carboxylate ion is mainly coordinated as shown in 1 and 2. In the unidentate complex (3), $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ is higher

than $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ is lower than $\nu_s(\text{CO}_2^-)$. As a result, the separation between the two ν_{COO} is much larger in unidentate complexes than in the free ion^{1,3}. The ir spectral band positions of the complexes are recorded in Table 2. If the 1655 and 1580 cm^{-1} bands in potassium malonate are taken as $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and the 1440 and 1410 cm^{-1} bands as $\nu_s(\text{COO})$, the separation of the two ν_{COO} bands in the two complexes $\text{K}_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ and $\text{K}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ is smaller than the free ion value. It may be suggested that the two complexes contain bidentate malonate rather than unidentate. The ratio of UO_2^{2+} : malonate in the complex $\text{K}_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ is 2:1, which suggests that it is a di- or poly-nuclear complex containing presumably bridging malonate. The antisymmetric and the symmetric COO bands in this complex appear closer to the free ion value. The exact way in which malonate is coordinated in this complex is difficult to conclude from the ir spectra. The fact that the spectra of these three complexes show the presence of traces of water (probably coming from KBr) which is evident from the appearance of weak bands near 3400 cm^{-1} , would

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL BANDS OF COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compd.	$\nu(\text{UO}_2)^a$	$\nu_{as}(\text{COO})^b$	$\nu_s(\text{COO})$
$\text{K}_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	940 vs, 910 vs	1 640 vs	1 450 vs
$\text{K}_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	925 vs, 890 vs	1 580 vs	1 410 vs
$\text{K}_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$	890 vs	1 590 vs	1 420 vs
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	900 vs	1 640 vs	1 460 vs ^c
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$	890 vs	1 590 vs	1 400 vs ^c
$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$	890 vs	1 590 vs	1 400 vs ^c
$\text{K}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4^d$		1 655 vs, 1 580 vs	1 440 vs, 1 410 vs, 1 365 vs

Overlapped with ν_{C-O} , ν_{O-O} and ν_{O-O-O} bands. ^bOverlapped with $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. ^cOverlapped with NH_4^+ bands.
^dIncluded for comparison.

suggest that any attempt to decide the mode of coordination of malonate from the position of the $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ band would only be a guess. The analysis of the ir spectra of the three ammonium compounds would also be difficult since the symmetrical COO band would be overlapped with the ν_4 mode of NH_4^+ which appears at about 1 400 cm⁻¹. However, it may be suggested that the malonate ion in $(\text{NH}_4)_2[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$, $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)]$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ is coordinated in the same manner as in the corresponding potassium compounds.

The assignment of the UO_2^{2+} bands in the complexes is also difficult since malonate gives absorption bands in the expected region. No attempt for the assignment of the U-F bands was made since malonate gives a number of bands below 650 cm⁻¹. It is, however, possible that some or all the complexes contain bridging fluoride.

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